

Short name	Trust in stakeholders	Long name	Public trust in various stakeholders impacts the acceptance
Geographical scope	National level		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Trust in main stakeholders, such as a government, is an important factor in risk perception and acceptance of technology ¹ . Higher trust in stakeholders leads to lower risk perception. It seems trust in governments and industry in the Nordic countries is higher ² cf. rest of Europe, particularly the Mediterranean sea region ³		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Trust in research and academic sectors and NGOs is consistently ranked high ⁴ . Consequently, the public relies on what they advocate or verify and prefers to involve with them in decision-making processes rather than stakeholders from industry.		
Other issues this affects	Trust should be considered in design of communication materials and process		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moon, W.-K.; Kahlor, L.A.; Olson, H.C. (2020). Understanding public support for carbon capture and storage policy: The roles of social capital, stakeholder perceptions, and perceived risk/benefit of technology. <i>Energy Policy</i>, 137, 111109. • Rodriguez, E., Lefvert, A., Fridahl, M., Grönkvist, S., Haikola, S., & Hansson, A. (2021). Tensions in the energy transition: Swedish and Finnish company perspectives on bioenergy with carbon capture and storage. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i>, 280, 124527. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652620345716 • Oltra, C., Dütschke, E., Preuß, S., Gonçalves, L., & Germán, S. (2022). What influences public attitudes and acceptance of CCUS technologies on the national and regional level? Results from a survey study in France and Spain. SSRN. • Tcvetkov, P.; Cherepovitsyn, A.; Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public 		

¹ Moon, W.-K.; Kahlor, L.A.; Olson, H.C. Understanding public support for carbon capture and storage policy: The roles of social capital, stakeholder perceptions, and perceived risk/benefit of technology. *Energy Policy* 2020

² Rodriguez, E., Lefvert, A., Fridahl, M., Grönkvist, S., Haikola, S., & Hansson, A. (2021). Tensions in the energy transition: Swedish and Finnish company perspectives on bioenergy with carbon capture and storage. *Journal of cleaner production*, 280, 124527. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652620345716>

³ 1) Oltra, C., Dütschke, E., Preuß, S., Gonçalves, L., & Germán, S. (2022). What influences public attitudes and acceptance of CCUS technologies on the national and regional level? Results from a survey study in France and Spain. Results from a survey study in France and Spain. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4272128

⁴ Tcvetkov, P.; Cherepovitsyn, A.; Fedoseev, S. Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon* 2019

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